

Awareness and attitude on issues of Covid-19 pandemic: Implications to science and technology education

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Abstract

The fast developments in technology become a necessity for people to be in constant touch with technology, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic. Various issues concerning science and technology (Quinto & Nieva, 2019) coupled with the challenges brought about by the online learning due to global health crisis, has pushed science technology innovations to develop different programs and supply the needed software and learning management systems. This descriptive-quantitative study attempts to determine the students' awareness and attitudes on some of the issues during this Covid-19 pandemic. A total of four hundred eighty-seven (487) students from St. Dominic College of Asia in Bacoor, Cavite were involved in the study. The study revealed that students have high to very high awareness of issues during the COVID-19 pandemic, same as with the attitudes. This would develop solutions for improvement in the preparedness of this technology crisis, likewise, can give insights on dealing with the youth that might affect their future schooling and the community. A qualitative approach should be explored in dealing with the issues of this COVID-19 pandemic.

Keywords: Awareness; Attitudes; Issues; COVID-19 pandemic; Science and technology education.

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Introduction

While COVID-19 has had a negative impact on many jobs and ways of life, technology has expanded its intrusion to make things easier (Pandey et al., 2021). People must stay in touch with technology constantly due to the rapid advancements in it, especially in light of the COVID-19 pandemic. Science and technology innovations, therefore, have developed different programs and supplied the software to adhere to the various issues concerning science and technology (Quinto & Nieva, 2019), coupled with the challenges brought about by online learning due to global health crises like the COVID-19 pandemic. However, college students lacked sufficient COVID-19 understanding and a high-risk perspective (Jiang, 2020) with the current online learning situation and the future that lies ahead of them. Moreover, the extent of knowledge of these advanced technological innovations in terms of privacy, domain knowledge, and user-friendliness has not been so explicitly examined in the literature, even though they are being used at a fast pace (Leslie, 2020).

Although the government has used technology to prevent and stop the rising number of COVID-19 cases, the public's support will largely depend on their awareness of and attitude toward those efforts (Pandey et al., 2021). Thus, their awareness and attitude toward the advancements of these science and technology issues and trends need to be addressed.

Concept of Attitude and Awareness

The study is anchored on the concept of the interrelatedness of attitude and awareness. Attitude is a particular feeling about a thing or an issue; it involves a tendency to behave in a certain way in situations that involve something. Moreover, an attitude provides a pattern of behavior that is a powerful source of motivation, arousal, and sustaining concentration efforts towards science and technology issues. As to Thurston's view, "*Attitude denotes the sum total of man's inclinations and feelings, prejudice or bias, per-conceived notions, ideas, fears, threats about any specific topic*". An attitude is a mental or neural set of readiness exerting direct dynamic influence upon the individual toward all objects and situations related to it. The students' attitude towards science and technology issues during the pandemic means their behavior or concern towards COVID-19 problems (WHO, 2021), climate change (Yli-Panula et al., 2022; UN, 2021), and information technology (Tomei, 2010). As for awareness, people have some beliefs and opinions about something. It is the students' opinions, ideas, and interests towards the COVID-19 problems or issues regarding science and technology that affect the climate and environment. Both awareness and attitude are interrelated. Awareness gives way to attitude; attitude paves the way for awareness (Satyanarayana, 2021).

Purpose of the Study

This research can determine the students' level of awareness and attitudes toward current issues in science and technology, such as COVID-19 variants and problems (WHO, 2021), climate change (UN, 2021), and information technology (Tomei, 2010). Because of these perceptions, the findings of this study can provide insights into how to deal with today's youth.

Methodology

To meet the aims of the study, a quantitative design framework was used to discover the awareness and attitudes of college students. This descriptive-quantitative study attempts to determine the students' awareness and attitudes toward some of the issues during this COVID-19 pandemic. Moreover, it aims to identify other issues focusing on science and technology in this current situation.

Participants

A total of four hundred eighty-seven (487) students from St. Dominic College of Asia in Bacoor, Cavite, were involved in the study. There were 392 students that came from the science programs and 95 from the non-science curricula taking up the Science, Technology, and Society (STS) subject in the general education core.

Data Collection Instrument and Procedures

A self-structured survey questionnaire was conducted using Google Forms. Data were gathered and collected using a Likert scale-type questionnaire and an open-ended question. The researchers created eight (8) statements pertaining to awareness and attitudes toward current issues in science and technology. The four (4) items pertaining to attitude and the four (4) items for awareness were considered. All the questions in the categories have been evaluated using a 5-point Likert scale, with 1 being strongly disagree, 2 being disagree, 3 being neither agree nor disagree, 4 being agree, and 5 being strongly agree.

The questionnaire was created and hosted using Google Forms. All the questions were marked as "mandatory" in order to submit the form, ensuring in this way that there will be no empty data cases. The questionnaire was validated by the research and development officer.

Data Analysis

After getting permission for the conduct of the study, the questionnaire was administered using social media platforms during a 30-day period. and was distributed to the students through Blackboard Learn, Messenger, and email from December 2021 to January 2022. The data were analyzed using frequency and percentage distributions. Statistical analysis was used through Microsoft Excel 2021.

Ethical Considerations

The objectives of the study were explained to the respondents, and the researchers informed them about voluntary participation and that the privacy and confidentiality of the research were protected. The data gathered was analyzed with accuracy and confidentiality. Likewise, the provisions of the Data Privacy Act of the Philippines were followed.

Results

Table 1. Awareness of students on the issues during COVID-19 pandemic

Statements	SA	A	N	D	SD
1. I know that the World Health Organization (WHO), the Philippine national government, and local health agencies should strictly and continuously impose the necessary measures and restrictions, e.g., hygienic, and protective measures, physical distancing, and travel bans, to prevent the widespread infection of the Covid-19 variants.	327 (67.15%)	142 (29.16%)	15 (3.08%)	2 (0.41%)	1 (0.21%)
2. The whole world is again facing another challenge nowadays due to the emergence of the Covid-19 variant known as Omicron believed to be more transmissible than the Delta variant. I am aware that with this development and the possible further mutations of Covid-19, it is most likely that the pandemic will continue for several more months.	201 (41.27%)	243 (49.90%)	39 (8.01%)	3 (0.62%)	1 (0.21%)
3. The advanced medical technology enabled the production of vaccines which is effective in preventing the infections from various Covid-19 variants. The vaccination program started with the adults, and then currently, to those with ages 17 years old and younger till 12 years old. The soon-to-be produced vaccines for the much younger children, i.e., 11 years old and below, will also be as effective.	223 (45.79%)	203 (41.68%)	57 (11.70%)	2 (0.41%)	2 (0.41%)
4. I know that most colleges and universities are employing Learning Management Systems (LMS) to implement the virtual education during this time of the pandemic.	213 (43.74%)	212 (43.53%)	55 (11.29%)	6 (1.23%)	1 (0.21%)

Legend: SA = strongly agree; A = agree; N = neither agree nor disagree; D = disagree; SD = strongly disagree

Table 1 determines the awareness of students about the issues during the COVID-19 pandemic. Four awareness statements were indicated in this table. Regarding awareness, on the first item, most students "strongly agree" that the World Health Organization (WHO), the Philippine national government, and local health agencies should strictly and continuously impose the necessary measures and restrictions, such as hygienic and protective measures, physical distancing, and travel bans, to prevent the widespread infection of the COVID-19 variants (67.15%). On the second item, the majority of the students "agree" that the whole world is again facing another challenge nowadays due to the emergence of the COVID-19 variant known as Omicron, believed to be more transmissible than the Delta variant (49.90%). On the third item, the majority of students "strongly agree" that advanced medical technology enabled the production of vaccines that are effective in preventing infections from various COVID-19 variants (45.79%). On the fourth item, most students "strongly agree" that most colleges and universities are employing learning management systems (LMS) to implement virtual education during this time of the pandemic (43.74%).

Table 2. Attitudes of students on the issues during COVID-19 pandemic

Statements	SA	A	N	D	SD
1. I believe that with the pandemic going on, it is still everyone's responsibility to help solve the issue of climate change, not only the world leaders and industrialists, but also ordinary citizens and students like us. Our contribution to this environmental concern would be significant.	342 (70.23%)	128 (26.28%)	17 (3.49%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)
2. With the rapid rise in the advances in information technology, people of all ages and walks of life have used it to their advantage to cope with the current pandemic.	225 (46.20%)	225 (46.20%)	35 (7.19%)	2 (0.41%)	0 (0.00%)
3. I believe that the current pandemic has greatly affected the education sector. We, students have no choice but to take online classes, and with the efforts put in by the schools, teachers, and students, the quality of education is at par with the pre-pandemic face-to-face mode of learning.	191 (39.22%)	207 (42.51%)	58 (11.91%)	22 (4.52%)	9 (1.85%)
4. Our school is currently using the Blackboard as the LMS for the online classes, and I am positive that it is effective in delivering synchronous and asynchronous lessons and activities.	213 (43.74%)	212 (43.53%)	55 (11.29%)	6 (1.23%)	1 (0.21%)

Legend: SA = strongly agree; A = agree; N = neither agree nor disagree; D = disagree; SD = strongly disagree

Table 2 describes the attitudes of students toward the issues during the COVID-19 pandemic. In terms of attitudes, on the first item, the majority of students "strongly agree" that with the pandemic going on, it is still everyone's responsibility to help solve the issue of climate change, not only the world leaders and industrialists but also ordinary citizens and students like them (70.23%). On the second item, most students both "strongly agree" and "agree" that with the rapid rise in advances in information technology, people of all ages and walks of life have used it to their advantage to cope with the current pandemic (46.20%). On the third item, the majority of students "agree" that the current pandemic has greatly affected the education sector and that the quality of education nowadays is at par with the pre-pandemic face-to-face mode of learning (42.51%). On the fourth item, most students "strongly agree" that this school is currently using Blackboard Learn as the LMS for the online classes and that they are positive about this effectiveness in delivering synchronous and asynchronous lessons and activities (43.74%).

Discussion

In Table 1, it shows that students are mostly aware of some of the issues that happened during the COVID-19 pandemic. They know that despite the pandemic, students can easily adapt to new ways of living, such as keeping themselves safe and learning through online education. This study confirms the findings of Santiago and Santos (2021), where students have good to very good knowledge of the COVID-19 pandemic, and Quansah et al. (2022), where the acceptance of COVID-19 risk perception among university students in Ghana is high, which states the higher levels of compliance with COVID-19 protocols on different campuses.

Based on the results in Table 2, students are mostly positive about their understanding of some of the issues encountered during this pandemic. It proves that students can cope very well with getting involved with online learning as well as being responsible for mitigating the effects of such environmental concerns, particularly climate change. In a study by Kuloglu and Yildiz (2022), the attitudes of the undergraduates were revealed to be "moderate". This shows that students are satisfied with the online learning platforms they use, as provided by their school. On the other hand, Liu et al. (2020) found that environmental attitudes have a great positive effect on environmental behavioral intentions and pro-environmental behaviors. It can be attributed to the fact that students are engaged in a "green lifestyle" that helps to minimize environmental problems, such as doing the 3 Rs (reducing, reusing, and recycling), using eco-friendly technologies, and joining different sustainable leisure activities such as eating organic foods, hiking or brisk walking, and riding a bicycle instead of commuting or driving in other vehicles.

A paper about the knowledge, attitudes, and practices toward COVID-19 and its associated factors was conducted among university students in Japan through a cross-sectional survey (Hatabu et al., 2020). Results indicated that gender, major subjects, education levels, nationality, residence, private self-consciousness, and extroversion are related to knowledge and attitudes toward COVID-19 (Hatabu et al., 2020). Although this is different from the current study, students from St. Dominic College of Asia are much better prepared to understand safety and deal with online education amidst the crisis.

Another study conducted by Reyes et al. (2021) revealed that higher levels of climate change anxiety have significantly lower mental health among Generation Z Filipino participants. Generation Z people tend to be more concerned with climate change today than adults. In fact, this is becoming increasingly normal when people try to understand the situations brought about by climate change. But emotional responses can be worsened by overthinking what will happen in the future; thus, it might be a problem that could affect their physical and mental health levels. Finding ways to minimize or cope with emotional responses amidst changing conditions will help them respond to such concerns without losing track of any social consequences (Clayton, 2020).

A study in Trinidad and Tobago was conducted about COVID-19 awareness among undergraduate medical students and found that the senior undergraduate students showed higher knowledge, attitude, and awareness levels than the first- and second-year students (Umakanthan et al., 2022). While students have sufficient knowledge of commonly exposed information (e.g., COVID-19 transmission, prevention, and symptoms), they still lack complete, detailed awareness of this disease. This is similar to the findings in Tables 1 and 2, where SDCA students have high to very high awareness and attitudes of the issues happening during the COVID-19 pandemic, but there is limited information on whether they fully promote the new ways of adapting to this current situation. Baloran (2020) suggested that higher educational institutions should improve their plans for handling outbreaks and pandemics that might affect nearby communities, especially in training Filipino students to use online resources considering potential health issues (e.g., emerging infectious diseases, mental health issues) or other community emergencies such as natural disasters and calamities. This can help students become enlightened about the things they can do to prevent the risk of COVID-19 and to support the activities done by the school and the organization.

Since awareness and attitudes towards the issues of the COVID-19 pandemic among students have become popular today, only a few studies have been conducted on the implications for science and technology

education in different countries. This study intends to understand more in other literature about the awareness and attitudes toward the issues of this pandemic to fill the gap in getting into science and technology education.

Conclusions

The study revealed that students have a high to very high awareness of issues during the COVID-19 pandemic, as well as attitudes. However, an attempt to investigate other COVID-19 issues is limited and not discussed further. Thus, further research is necessary to expound on the results. A qualitative approach should also be explored to identify the critical uncertainties brought by the pandemic and distinguish policies that would optimize new technological capabilities and build resilience, including future disruptive changes at the systemic level and possible implications for science and technology education and innovation. This would develop solutions for improving the preparedness for this ongoing crisis as well as calamities that might affect the community and the school. Future studies may determine demographic variables that could affect the awareness and attitudes of students towards COVID-19 issues and explore the effects of COVID-19, climate change, and information technology on the students they encounter in this circumstance.

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